

VeriFish

The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns

Project Title	The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns
Project Acronym	VeriFish
Project Number	101156426
Type of project	HORIZON-CSA HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Topics	HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01
Starting date of Project	01 May 2024
Duration of the project	24 months
Website	www.verifish.info

D4.2 – Good Practice Recommendation

Work Package	WP4 Develop a European Good Practice recommendation (CWA) for how to communicate on seafood
Task	T4.2 CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA)
Lead author	Silje Steinsbø (Nofima)
Contributors	Petter Olsen (Nofima) Organizations and individuals that developed and approved the CEN Workshop Agreement: Blue Food Performance, Clupea, COMMpla, Cromaris EATIP, EC, EFFOP, EuroCommerce, EUROFIR, EuroFish, Europêche, FAO, Federación Regional de Cofradías de Pescadores de Canarias, FISH.COOP.FRIŠKA, FORTH, ICES, Lantern innovation, MGF3.0, Moceans Environmental Consultants, Nofima, Oceana, OAGAC, Poseidon, Submariner, Trust-IT, University of Galway, West Pomeranian University of Technology in Szczecin, WWF
Peer reviewers	Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)
Version	V1.0
Due Date	30/04/26
Submission Date	29/04/26

Dissemination Level

X	PU: Public, fully open
	SEN: Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
	Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
	Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
	Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

VeriFish

The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	27/04/20526	Silje Steinsbø (Nofima)	First draft
0.2	29/04/2026	Petter Olsen (Nofima)	Full complete version
1.0	29/04/2026	Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)	Final version for upload

Keywords

VeriFish, seafood, consumer, communication, seafood types, seafood consumers, consumer types, communication strategies, fisheries, fishery, wild catch, wild harvest, aquaculture, farmed seafood

Disclaimer

VeriFish offers a framework of verifiable sustainability indicators for communications about sustainability based on FAIR data from EU- and global aquafoods repositories, brought together through the extraordinary collaboration of European-wide actors. Leveraging on this indicator, VeriFish designs, develops, and disseminates a number of media products to help citizens, seafood consumers and retailers, associations and policy makers make informed consumption choices.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
ADI	Acceptable Daily Intake
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LLM	Large Language Model
QR-code	Quick Response Code, a two-dimensional matrix barcode

Executive Summary

The VeriFish Good Practice recommendation is intended as a practical tool for actors involved in seafood communication and marketing, supporting the design of campaigns that engage consumers more effectively. This recommendation is published as a low-level, voluntary European standard which will be distributed by the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) as a CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA). The CWA is designed to help the seafood industry communicate with consumers about their products, and the aim is to support an increase in sustainable seafood consumption.

This report (D4.2 – “Good Practice Recommendation”) is linked to task 4.2 – “CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA)” within VeriFish and is based on VeriFish D4.1 – “Initial Recommendation for how to efficiently communicate to consumers about seafood”, which drew on inputs and experiences from WP2 and WP3, as well as existing literature and established knowledge on the issue. The content of this document describes the outcome of the CWA process after extensive stakeholder consultation, hearing periods, and a consensus meeting. The content of this deliverable (from Table of Content and onwards) was sent to the CWA secretariat (Standard Norway) for publication in April 2026, and unless minor editorial changes are made, reflects what the content of the officially published CWA will be. Through CEN, the recommendations will be published as a voluntary European standard, which may serve as a foundation for future implementations, Good Practice recommendations or higher-level standards (e.g. CEN or ISO). The details around the CWA process are described in D4.3 – “Documentation of the consensus-driven CWA process”.

Following the introduction, this report is structured in four chapters: 1 Scope, 2 Terms and definitions, 3 General principles for seafood marketing, and 4 Recommendations for seafood marketing.

Chapter 3 General principles for seafood marketing, sets out principles for effective seafood marketing by emphasizing consumer segmentation (consumer types), product differentiation (seafood types), and contextual communication. The chapter highlights the importance of aligning communication with everyday consumer needs, values and decision-making processes. It also underscores the growing role of digital tools and media channels.

Chapter 4 Recommendations for seafood marketing, translates the general principles into recommendations for seafood marketing. It stresses the importance of defining target audiences and adapting messages to appropriate channels and formats. The chapter also have a recommendations table which outlines what information to highlight for different consumer and seafood type combinations. Finally, it addresses potential and limitations of using Artificial Intelligence as a support tool, emphasizing accuracy and regulatory compliance.

Chapter 4 is accompanied by Annex A.1 and A.2, which provides two examples on how the recommendations table (Table 1) can be used by seafood companies. Additionally, Annex B presents an example of how Large Language Models can be used as an assisting tool in targeted seafood campaigns.

TABLE OF CONTENT

Introduction	4
1 Scope.....	4
2 Terms and definitions	5
Seafood	5
3 General principles for seafood marketing	5
3.1 Introduction	5
3.2 Intended application and potential users	5
3.3 Consumer types.....	5
3.4 Seafood types	6
3.5 Communication strategies	7
3.6 Use of Artificial Intelligence / Large Language Models	7
4 Recommendations for seafood marketing	8
4.1 General	8
4.2 Communication strategies	8
4.3 Recommendation for what information to include to efficiently communicate with consumers	9
Table 1 Recommendations for what information to include to efficiently communicate with consumers about seafood	10
4.4 Artificial Intelligence / Large Language Models	12
Annex A (informative) Examples of how to use Table 1.....	13
A.1 Example 1: Cod fillet products from fishery for health-conscious consumers	13
A.2 Example 2: Seabass from aquaculture for familiarity-driven consumers	14
Annex B (informative) Examples of how to use Large Language Models (LLMs).....	15
B.1 Example 3: Shrimp and “räkfrossa” in the Swedish market.....	15
Annex C (informative) Consumer types.....	19
Bibliography	20

Introduction

The VeriFish CWA provides Good Practice recommendations on how to effectively engage and influence different consumer groups to encourage sustainable seafood consumption. Rather than defining concepts such as “local”, “seasonal”, “nutritious”, or “healthy”, this document focuses on how such attributes can be communicated more effectively. The recommendations aim to support the design of targeted seafood communication and marketing campaigns by ensuring that relevant, verifiable content is presented in ways that are more likely to influence purchasing behaviour.

The target audience for this CWA includes public and private organisations involved in the design or implementation of seafood communication or promotion campaigns. It is intended to support actors seeking guidance on how to prioritise messages and communication approaches based on specific seafood products and target consumer groups. The initiative responds to an expressed need from seafood stakeholders and communicators across Europe for practical, harmonised guidance in this field.

The objective of this CWA is to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of seafood communication and marketing campaigns, enabling them to reach and influence diverse consumer groups within budget constraints and existing legislation. In the longer term, the recommendations aim to contribute to increased consumption, production, and availability of sustainable seafood.

By formalizing communication strategies in a CEN Workshop Agreement, it is ensured that the recommendations will not only be widely accessible, but also officially recognized and distributed through national standardization bodies.

1 Scope

This document provides recommendations on how to efficiently communicate with consumers about seafood and to engage and influence various types of consumers to encourage consumption of sustainable seafood. Seafood as part of a meal also containing non-seafood ingredients, e.g. ready-to-eat meals, is included in this document.

This document excludes:

food or feed for species other than humans

food items with only a small fraction of seafood

dietary supplements.

This document does not differentiate between information elements that are mandatory to share (e.g. because of labelling regulations) and information elements that are voluntary. That is partly because the legally required information elements represent a minimum and need to be communicated

regardless of any recommendations, and partly because various labelling regulations exist in different domains. The objective of this CWA is to make these recommendations generally relevant and applicable.

This document does not go into detail on how claims made in a marketing campaign might be verified, nor does it recommend communicating information elements that are likely to be perceived as negative by the consumer. The reason is that while verification and the ability to substantiate a claim is important, it is not normally part of a marketing campaign (and neither is the highlighting of information that is unlikely to elicit a positive reaction). An exception to this is certification status that can constitute indirect verification of some claims, and which it may be relevant to communicate in some circumstances.

2 Terms and definitions

Seafood

All types of food for humans originating from all types of aquatic environments.

3 General principles for seafood marketing

3.1 Introduction

Effective communication about seafood requires detailed knowledge of consumer segments, product types, and geographical contexts. Understanding the specific needs and perceptions of different consumer groups in particular is essential for fostering a more sustainable seafood market.

3.2 Intended application and potential users

The recommendations are intended as a practical tool for actors involved in seafood communication and marketing, supporting the design of campaigns that aim to engage consumers more effectively. The CWA is designed to help the seafood industry communicate with consumers about their products. Ultimately, the aim is to support an increase in sustainable seafood consumption.

All recommendations are intended to be used by those who comply with national and international legislation regarding procurement, production, labelling, and marketing of seafood products.

3.3 Consumer types

Efficient communication about seafood is complex and will vary across different consumer groups, product types, and regions. To effectively promote sustainable choices, communication strategies should be tailored to specific audiences, considering a wide range of factors.

Consumers choose food based on practical needs like cooking skills, taste, dietary preferences, and available time. Understanding these everyday decisions helps in designing messages and campaigns that resonate with different groups. Price also plays a role; affordable options and smart pricing strategies can encourage healthier and more sustainable choices.

Consumers may be categorised across multiple dimensions, including demographic characteristics, purchasing channels, and core personal values. While research offers a wide range of segmentation approaches, certain consumer profiles are common across a range of studies. Based on this, three broad consumer types are identified and described below.

- **Health-conscious:** Prioritizes the health benefits and nutritional value associated with seafood consumption.
- **Environmentally and ethically motivated:** Focuses on sustainability and ethical considerations.
- **Familiarity-driven:** Sticks to familiar seafood types and recipes.

3.4 Seafood types

Effective communication strategies should differentiate seafood in ways that are relevant to consumer preferences and decision-making contexts. In this recommendation, seafood is categorised based on how consumers use products to fulfil specific needs (jobs-to-be-done). This approach aligns with established practices in seafood marketing and consumer research.

The four categories are organized on two levels:

- Level 1 seafood types:
 - **Fisheries** – *For seafood acquired from the wild.*
 - **Aquaculture** – *For farmed seafood.*
- Level 2 seafood types:
 - **In need of preparation** – *A range composed of raw products, products with a low degree of processing (e.g., fillets, gutted fish), and whole products, etc. Products of this type typically require some preparation and treatment before consumption.*
 - **Ready-to-eat** – *A range of products largely ready to eat and/or ready for temperature treatment. Examples include fish gratin, fish cakes, fish sticks, fish burgers, seaweed chips, canned products, caviar, peeled shrimps, etc.*

Seafood from fisheries and aquaculture share certain characteristics, but also differ in ways that have implications for how to efficiently communicate to different types of consumers. Differences in regulatory frameworks, technological needs, inputs like feed, certification schemes etc., mean that the relevant attributes to use in communication vary.

There is not a clear line between the level 2 categories “In need of preparation” and “Ready-to-eat”, but there are several distinctions that can be made when communicating to different consumer types. For example, recipes are particularly relevant for the “In need of preparation” products.

A single seafood product can simultaneously originate from wild caught and farmed conditions, for example ranched tuna. In this case (e.g. capture-based aquaculture or a product containing a mix of seafood sources), it may be relevant to communicate the most appropriate attributes from both categories.

3.5 Communication strategies

An increasingly popular method for communicating to the consumer is the presence of a QR-code (square barcode) on the package, menu, or in the shop. The consumer can scan this and get additional information about the product in question. This is a cheap and versatile way to communicate specific information to consumers who might be interested and willing to invest the effort related to scanning and reading.

Different consumer groups access information through different communication channels and formats. Evidence consistently shows generational differences in media consumption habits, with younger consumers relying more heavily on digital platforms, including social media, while older consumers tend to depend more on traditional media such as television and print.

Also, a generational division can be found in the use of social media platforms. Even though Facebook remains the most popular media channel, its use has decreased among younger adults that are more likely to use a variety of other platforms, including Instagram, YouTube, TikTok, and Snapchat.

3.6 Use of Artificial Intelligence / Large Language Models

Generative Artificial Intelligence (Gen AI) offers a potential valuable tool for small and medium-sized businesses to enhance their communication and marketing efforts. It can assist them in reaching a broader audience and get across complex messages about seafood, especially where resources and specialised staff are limited.

A range of AI-based tools is currently available to support text generation, content structuring, image creation and data handling. The field is evolving rapidly, and new tools and applications are being released continuously.

AI enables small and medium-sized businesses to market their own products cost-effectively with minimal resources, compared to large international players with greater financial power and daily access to such technologies [1]. If properly trained and with appropriate prompts, AI can be used to structure efficient marketing campaigns for a given seafood product, in a given geographical area, aimed at a defined consumer group. In the appendix we have provided an example of this.

4 Recommendations for seafood marketing

4.1 General

This section provides a structured set of recommendations for communicating the sustainability of seafood products, tailored to specific consumer profiles and seafood categories.

4.2 Communication strategies

When planning a communication strategy, the first, and most important element is to decide *who* the target group is. Different groups interpret and prioritize sustainability in different ways. Communication should be adapted in both tone and content to suit the expectations, knowledge levels, and motivations of each audience segment.

Channels for reaching seafood consumers can vary depending on the target group, but examples of possible useful channels include media articles – mass media or specific media, social media, brochures, TV ads, campaigns, posters, events, stands, cooking events with chefs, books, recipes, websites and more as well as information provided directly alongside the product by the seller or on the label.

Social media represents an important communication channel across multiple age groups, particularly among younger consumers. For a small business, trying to increase their sale of seafood, social media offers a free, accessible and potentially very engaging channel to promote their seafood. Understanding how the target group interacts, engages and consumes content on each platform is also an important consideration.

At the very core of every campaign or communication activity lies the message. The message should focus on the take-home message for the audience in question. The take-home message should take into consideration both the target audience and the chosen channels for the campaign. While “lowering your carbon footprint through eating more sustainable food” makes up for a valid argument for the environmental and ethical consumer, it might not resonate with the price-sensitive consumer.

When creating the message of the campaign, you should remember the principle of communication. Messages should not only inform but engage and ideally motivate the target group to change their consumption patterns. e.g. through comments, sharing of web-content, repeated site visits, etc. This could mean aligning sustainability narratives with personal values — health, price, convenience, or environmental impact — depending on the audience.

The key message should align with both target audience and chosen channel. Opportunities and constraints in each communication channel needs to be considered in the design of the message. Some platforms favour short, visual formats, while others allow and encourage more detailed contextual information to be presented.

Effective campaign design requires consideration of who the target audience is, where they can be reached, and what message and format are most appropriate to convey the intended information.

Concrete examples of social media campaigns:

For health-conscious consumers: Cooking and/or preparing a healthy meal short video / reel. Focus on nutrition, vitamins, and minerals and how it benefits your health.

For environmental and ethical consumers: From ocean/water to plate visualisations.

For familiarity driven consumers: “How to” prepare seafood short reels / videos, traditional dishes, and traditional dishes with a twist.

4.3 Recommendation for what information to include to efficiently communicate with consumers

Table 1 contains recommended information to highlight regardless of seafood types as outlined in Section 5.4 “Seafood types”. The intention of having the recommendation of information to highlight in a table is to make the combination of chosen consumer types and seafood types visible. In Annex A there are two examples indicating how the table can be used.

With respect to the information elements highlighted in the table and used when communicating, it is of course important that these elements give a truthful depiction of the actual situation and that means of verification exist.

Table 1 Recommendations for what information to include to efficiently communicate with consumers about seafood

Table 1 Recommendations for what information to include to efficiently communicate with consumers about seafood by information that can apply to different consumer types and different seafood types in general (in dark blue cells), and what could be effective to highlight for level 1 seafood types (fisheries and aquaculture), level 2 seafood types (in need of preparation and ready for meal) for three specified consumer types (health-conscious, environmental and ethical, and familiarity driven) respectively.

Consumer type → Seafood type ↓		Applies to most consumer types	Health-conscious	Environmental and Ethical	Familiarity driven
Applies to most seafood types		+Species +Nutrition declaration +Certification status +CO ₂ eq/kg + Production method, i.e. whether the origin is from aquaculture or fisheries +Provenance	+Nutritional claims (e.g. Omega 3, high-quality protein, micronutrients, low sodium) +Health claims (e.g. cardiovascular health, immune function) +Recommended acceptable daily intake (ADI)	+Climate change adaptation +Animal welfare measures +Fair trade practices	+Link with region / location +Link to local history, tradition, or culture
L e v e l 1	Fishery	+Harvest method / gear type +Catch area		+Stock status +Country of origin, flag state +Participation in Fishery Improvement Projects +Habitat impact +Bait use	+Stock status +Country of origin, flag state
	Aquaculture	+Feed type +Non-fed	+Production system +Feed +Medication (antibiotics)	+Production system (interaction with environment) +Management compliance (areal, quantity limitations, work conditions)	+Social licence to operate (esp. visual impact)

	Consumer type → Seafood type ↓	Applies to most consumer types	Health-conscious	Environmental and Ethical	Familiarity driven
L e v e l 2	“In need of preparation”	+Seafood preparation instruction videos +Preparation method (simple and quick)	+Healthy recipes	+Sustainable recipes	+Recipes with new species +Traditional recipes
	“Ready for meal”		+Seafood percentage +Nutritional claims (added ingredients) +Suggestions for healthy side dishes +Allergens	+Suggestions for sustainable side dishes +Information on packaging sustainability	+Suggestions for other species that taste similarly

4.4 Artificial Intelligence / Large Language Models

If choosing to use an AI tool, it is important to consider known weaknesses, such as the possibility that text or sustainability claims may be fabricated or contain factual inaccuracies. Incorrect facts or misleading claims in seafood marketing may be subject to legislation and might be illegal. Therefore, having updated knowledge and a reliable knowledge base is crucial. The European Commission provides an online resource that compiles knowledge across five key areas: Organisation of the Sector, Marketing Standards, Consumer Information, Competition Rules, and Market Intelligence [2]. It is also important to take in to account the EU general data protection regulation (GDPR).

AI tools can support marketing efforts in a cost-effective way, by helping with campaign planning, suggesting target segments, generating promotional materials, images, websites, and social media content in multiple languages. It also supports translations, budget estimations, and much more.

Note that generative AI can produce inaccurate or misleading content; outputs must be carefully reviewed, verified, and corrected before use.

Annex A **(informative)** **Examples of how to use Table 1**

This section contains two examples on how the recommendations table (Table 1) can be used by seafood companies.

A.1 Example 1: Cod fillet products from fishery for health-conscious consumers

We want to communicate and promote consumption of cod fillet products. In this example, the target audience is people with a low seafood consumption who are interested in consuming healthy protein rich food from the sea. We therefore focus on the health-conscious consumer type. Having cod fillets from fisheries, we then take the dark blue recommendations as a starting point and provide information about the species, nutrition declaration, certifications, catch location and CO₂ emissions. We also provide information about nutritional claims, health claims and recommended acceptable daily intake. The product type is in need of preparation, so we also provide healthy recipes. The media types that fit this type of promotion could be visual representation of nutrition facts, health claims, low on fat – fact sheets and more, ideal for social media (SoMe), product pages, and web site posters from the producer.

When crafting campaigns for cod fillet products for the health-conscious consumer type, your channel and message should be adapted to the target group; the health-conscious consumer type. Successful campaigns by the Norwegian Seafood Council have shown influencers demonstrating how to cook and prepare fish fillet in short, entertaining social media videos. As the health-conscious consumer is particularly interested in nutritional value, the benefits of the nutrients of the cod can be added during the cooking of the cod.

In all communication campaigns, it is important to address the target group either directly or indirectly. When creating social media videos this can be done through referring to issues or problems that the target group can relate to. For the health-conscious consumer, a concern could be to include sufficient protein in their diet and increase their uptake of Omega-3 which can reduce inflammation. Adding information like this, presented as a problem or concern that the target group can relate to will increase their engagement in your campaign. One way to do this is to ask questions like “do you struggle with getting enough lean protein in your diet”.

A.2 Example 2: Seabass from aquaculture for familiarity-driven consumers

In the case of promoting farmed seabass to consumers, we can focus on the familiarity driven consumer type, that would mostly consume cod or salmon, depending on their location. We then start from the dark blue recommendations and provide information about the species, nutrition declaration, fed/non-fed, certifications (if present) and CO2 emissions if a LCA has been conducted. Additionally, we provide information about the link of the product with the region it comes from and how this could influence the local economy, tradition and potential history-based storytelling about the area it comes from, preferably linked to local or regional culture (e.g. fishing tradition).

Since it is farmed fish, information on connection and contribution to local community could be particularly beneficial, and recipes that promote the taste of this new species, close to some traditional ones, would be positive elements to consider. Social media is a channel well suited to introduce new species, evoke curiosity and explain in an educational and entertaining manner how to prepare these species. Short and catchy films could be an entertaining format for inspiring these consumers, suited to combine both the familiar (known recipes) with unfamiliar species. Short films are also a format that works well to present delicious and tasty dishes. Several social media platforms' algorithms will help promote your content, if the format, the tags and your engagement hits the target group, showing tasty food films to hungry consumers.

Annex B (informative) **Examples of how to use Large Language Models (LLMs)**

This section contains an example of how Large Language Models can be used as an assisting tool in targeted seafood campaigns. Users of LLMs must remember to fact-check any proposals and make sure that the recommendations do not clash with regulations.

The example concerns shrimp and “räkfrossa” in the Swedish market.

B.1 Example 3: Shrimp and “räkfrossa” in the Swedish market

The use of ChatGPT 4.0 app from OpenAI was tested as a tool to plan and execute a marketing campaign for a seafood product as a case. The purpose was to assess the quality and documentation of the AI-generated output. The overall framework was as follows:

- Create a marketing campaign for shrimp in the Swedish market
- Producer is a small company with 15 employees and an administrative staff of 3, including one person responsible for marketing
- The budget is €5000, and costs should be distributed across the recommended activities
- The tool should propose market segments and campaign activities
- The message must be health-oriented, legally compliant, and based on environmentally friendly and certified stock

Marketing Campaign Plan: Shrimp & 'Räkfrossa' in the Swedish Market

Prompt

“I need to create a targeted marketing campaign for shrimp in the Swedish market related to the tradition “Räkfrossa”. Please provide a complete campaign plan that includes audience segmentation, recommended activities, messaging, and budget distribution.

◆ Producer Profile:

- A small seafood company with 15 employees
- Administration team of 3 people, including one marketing responsible
- Preference for low administrative workload

◆ Budget:

- Total marketing budget: €5000
- Distribute costs across the proposed activities with clear breakdown

◆ Campaign Objective and Message:

- Promote fresh shrimp that are:
 - o Environmentally friendly caught
 - o From a certified stock
 - o Known for health benefits (e.g. high in protein, low in fat)
 - o In line with food safety regulations
- The message must be truthful, engaging, and trust-building

◆ What I need from you:

- 1) Suggested consumer segments to target in Sweden
- 2) Recommended marketing activities and channels (e.g. social media, local ads, retailer partnerships)
- 3) A core campaign message and optional slogan
- 4) Budget breakdown by activity
- 5) Use of free or low-cost European tools where appropriate

Producer Profile

- A small seafood company with 15 employees
- Administration team of 3 people, including one marketing responsible
- Preference for low administrative workload

Budget Overview

- Total marketing budget: €5000
- Costs are distributed across the proposed activities with a clear breakdown”

Result given by Chat GPT - Campaign Objective and Message

This campaign aims to promote fresh shrimp aligned with the Swedish summer tradition of 'Räkfrossa'. The shrimp are:

- Environmentally friendly caught
- From a certified stock
- Known for health benefits (e.g. high in protein, low in fat)
- In line with food safety regulations

The message must be truthful, engaging, and trust-building.

Target Consumer Segments

- Summer Vacationers & Cottage Owners (Ages 30–65):
 - Looking for seasonal, social food experiences in coastal areas
- Restaurants & Caterers:
 - Require fresh, high-quality, certified shrimp for seafood events
- Young Food Enthusiasts (Ages 25–40):
 - Trend-aware and interested in sustainability
 - Highly active on social media

Recommended Marketing Activities & Channels

Social Media Campaign: 'Räkfrossa inspiration' via Instagram and Facebook (recipes, feast images, UGC (User Generated Content, like Photos, Video, Text and more) contest)

- Meta Ads: Location-based ads promoting shrimp freshness and eco-certification
- Shrimp Feast Packs: Bundle deals with shrimp and Räkfrossa-themed items
- Restaurant Collaboration: Posters, branded menus for seafood events
- Email Campaign: Tips, recipes, shrimp sustainability info (Brevo or MailerLite)
- Instagram Contest: Share your shrimp feast – Win a shrimp pack!

Core Campaign Message & Slogan

Core Message:

“Nothing says Swedish summer like a shrimp feast. Enjoy fresh, certified shrimp – good for your health, good for the sea.”

Slogan Options:

- Taste the Summer – The Shrimp Feast Starts Here
- Shrimp That Do Good – For You and the Sea
- Fresh. Real. Certified.

Budget Breakdown (€5000)

- Meta Ads: €1200 – Targeted for 3 weeks in coastal towns
- Social Content & Contest: €600 – Design + prize (shrimp pack)
- Restaurant Materials (Flyers/Posters): €400 – Distributed to 10 partners
- Email Campaign: €250 – Brevo or MailerLite setup + content creation
- Influencer Collaboration: €900 – 1–2 micro-influencers (Instagram)
- Design & Content Production: €550 – Canva Pro, freelance support
- Contingency/Boosting: €1100 – Flexible budget for performance-based spend

Suggested Free/Low-Cost European Tools

- Canva (EU-based data storage available): Visual design
- Brevo (EU-based, formerly Sendinblue): Email campaigns
- MailerLite (EU/GDPR compliant): Email marketing and automation
- Meta Ads Manager: Facebook/Instagram ad targeting
- Freepik / Pexels (EU-supported): Royalty-free imagery
- Typeform (Spain-based): Forms for contests or product sign-ups

Summary

This campaign connects the traditional Swedish Råkfrossa with sustainably caught, health-forward shrimp. It empowers a small seafood producer to reach consumers through culturally relevant, digital-first strategies using cost-efficient tools, with seasonal storytelling and targeted advertising at its core.

Annex C (informative) Consumer types

The communication of sustainability in seafood consumption is a multifaceted issue that varies significantly across different consumer segments, product types, and geographical areas in Europe. Understanding these variations is crucial for developing effective strategies to promote sustainable seafood consumption and thus designing communication material. Successful campaigns will take these variations into consideration by designing communication that targets consumer segments, taking cultural differences into account.

To effectively market seafood to consumers in Europe, it is essential to tailor the messaging based on geographical areas, cultural contexts, and whether consumers live inland or by the coast.

Defining food categories and their organisation can become a long and complicated endeavour. One way of organising food categories is for what they offer to the consumer in terms of day-to-day solutions. The "Jobs to be Done" (JTBD) framework [3] analyses consumer behaviour in supermarkets by positing that consumers "hire" products to fulfil specific tasks or solve problems in their daily lives. This framework highlights that consumers engage in sub-goals or "job steps" when shopping, such as selecting ingredients for a warm dinner based on cooking skills, dietary preferences, and time constraints. Bettencourt et al. emphasize defining the job independently of the means to avoid myopia in assisting consumers. Diderich [4] discusses value creation in demand-driven markets, stressing the importance of understanding customer segments and their specific jobs. Price sensitivity influences consumer choices, with research showing that pricing strategies can stimulate healthier food choices [5] [6] [7]. Note that the effects of price promotions vary across product categories, influenced by relationships between items. Aligning product offerings with consumer jobs enhances satisfaction, optimizes pricing strategies, and creates effective promotional campaigns.

Bibliography

- [1] Haleem, A., Javaid, M., Qadri, M. A., Singh, R. P., & Suman, R. (2022). Artificial intelligence (AI) applications for marketing: A literature-based study. *International Journal of Intelligent Networks*, 3, 119-132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijin.2022.08.005>
- [2] European Commission, Sustainable fisheries, Markets and trade, Seafood markets. https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/fisheries/markets-and-trade/seafood-markets_en
- [3] Bettencourt, L., Harmeling, C., Bhagwat-Rana, Y., & Houston, M. (2021). Consumer job journeys. *Journal of Service Research*, 25(3), 347-370. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10946705211032501>
- [4] Diderich, C. (2024). An axiomatic model towards understanding value creation and appropriation in demand-driven markets. *Journal of Strategy and Management*, 17(2), 375-390. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jsma-11-2023-0299>
- [5] Jia, N., Jin, S., Chen, G., & Geng, X. (2024). How can price promotions make consumers more interested? an empirical study from a chinese supermarket. *Sustainability*, 16(6), 2512. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16062512>
- [6] Ravensbergen, E., Waterlander, W., Kroeze, W., & Steenhuis, I. (2015). Healthy or unhealthy on sale? a cross-sectional study on the proportion of healthy and unhealthy foods promoted through flyer advertising by supermarkets in the netherlands. *BMC Public Health*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-015-1748-8>
- [7] Waterlander, W., Steenhuis, I., Boer, M., Schuit, A., & Seidell, J. (2012). The effects of a 25% discount on fruits and vegetables: results of a randomized trial in a three-dimensional web-based supermarket. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 9(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1479-5868-9-11>